

Dielectric Studies of Charge Transfer Interactions between 1,2-Dibromoethane and some Aromatic Hydrocarbons in Liquid State

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Manuscript received 9 March 1992, revised 15 June 1992, accepted 17 June 1992

The study of excess molar volumes of mixing and excess molar enthalpies of mixing^{1,2} and excess molar Gibbs free energy of mixing^{3,4} of 1,2-dibromoethane with aromatic hydrocarbons have shown the existence of weak specific interactions of electron donor/acceptor type in which the aromatic hydrocarbon behaves as electron donor. Buep and Baron⁵ developed a simple model for donor/acceptor type complex formation based on the additivity of electronic susceptibilities of the components in the binary mixtures and their model provides a direct relationship between the experimental values of permittivity/refractive index and excess value for these components. In the present investigations excess dielectric constants and refractive indices for mixtures of DBE+benzene, +toluene, +*o*-xylene and +*m*-xylene over the whole composition range at 308.15 K have been obtained. Our earlier reported activity coefficient data³ have been used to confirm the complexation reactions using an ideal associated model approach⁶. The data obtained have been

coupled with the activity coefficient data of these mixtures, and Buep and Baron model has been applied to confirm the presence of donor/acceptor type complex formation in these mixtures.

Results and Discussion

Excess values of dielectric constants (ϵ^E) and excess squared refractive indices (η^{2E}) for *D*-lines for DBE (A)+benzene (B), +toluene (B), +*o*-xylene (B) and +*m*-xylene (B) mixtures over the whole composition range were calculated and are shown graphically in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. The excess values were fitted to equation (1).

$$Y^E = \phi_A (1 - \phi_A) [a_1 + a_2(2\phi_A - 1) + a_3(2\phi_A - 1)^2] \quad (1)$$

where Y^E is the excess property, e.g. ϵ^E or η^{2E} , and ϕ_A is volume fraction of component A; the fitted parameters a_1 , a_2 and a_3 were evaluated by the method of least-squares and are given together with the standard deviations (σ) in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF a_1 , a_2 , a_3 ALONGWITH STANDARD DEVIATIONS (σ) OF ϵ^E AND η^{2E} FOR DBE (A)+AROMATIC HYDROCARBON (B) MIXTURES AT 308.15 K

System		a_1	a_2	a_3	(σ) ϵ^E OR η^{2E}
DBE+Benzene	ϵ^E	-0.012 1	0.586 8	0.083 8	0.016
	η^{2E}	-32.12 $\times 10^{-3}$	2.50 $\times 10^{-3}$	-4.82 $\times 10^{-3}$	0.000 3
DBE+Toluene	ϵ^E	-0.226 2	0.800 1	0.146 8	0.008
	η^{2E}	-31.90 $\times 10^{-3}$	4.11 $\times 10^{-3}$	41.70 $\times 10^{-3}$	0.000 5
DBE+ <i>o</i> -Xylene	ϵ^E	-0.966 2	0.552 9	-0.205 7	0.009
	η^{2E}	-47.79 $\times 10^{-3}$	8.88 $\times 10^{-3}$	12.22 $\times 10^{-3}$	0.000 5
DBE+ <i>m</i> -Xylene	ϵ^E	-0.658 6	0.441 2	-0.002 9	0.006
	η^{2E}	-52.64 $\times 10^{-3}$	-1.59 $\times 10^{-3}$	-40.02 $\times 10^{-3}$	0.000 9

Fig. 1. Excess permittivities (ϵ^E) at 308.15 K for: (○) DBE + benzene, (●) DBE + toluene, (□) DBE + *o*-xylene and (▲) DBE + *m*-xylene.

Fig. 2. Excess refractive indices (η^{2E}) at 308.15 K for: (○) DBE + benzene, (●) DBE + toluene, (□) DBE + *o*-xylene and (▲) DBE + *m*-xylene.

The excess permittivities of mixing of DBE with *o*-xylene or *m*-xylene are negative for all volume fractions but those of DBE with benzene or toluene are negative upto volume fractions 0.53 and 0.67 respectively and become positive thereafter. The order of variation of ϵ^E at equivolume fraction is DBE+benzene > DBE+toluene > DBE+*m*-xylene > DBE+*o*-xylene. The excess squared refractive indices for all the mixtures are negative at all volume fractions and the order of variation of magnitude at equivolume fractions of (η^{2E}) is DBE+benzene > DBE+toluene > DBE+*o*-xylene > DBE+*m*-xylene.

Buep and Baron⁴ proposed a simple model based on the additivity of electrical susceptibilities of the components in a mixture involving a donor/acceptor type 1:1 complex formation. Since we suspected charge transfer complexation in our binary systems, therefore, we applied Buep and Baron model⁵ to our experimental data. The values of equilibrium constants were obtained from our earlier reported activity coefficient data³ for these mixtures which in turn were calculated from vapour pressure data using the ideal associated model⁶.

In ideal associated model, it is assumed that in these mixtures the equilibrium process occurs according to the reaction, $A+B \rightleftharpoons AB$. The three species A, B and AB are assumed to mix ideally. If Z_A , Z_B and Z_{AB} are the equilibrium mole fractions of species A, B and AB respectively, then the equilibrium constant (K_{AM}) is given by

$$K_{AM} = Z_{AB} / (Z_A Z_B) \text{ or } Z_{AB} = K_{AM} Z_A Z_B \quad (2)$$

Also at equilibrium,

$$Z_A + Z_B + Z_{AB} = 1 \quad (3)$$

and combining equations (2) and (3) we get,

$$(1 - Z_A - Z_B) / Z_B = K_{AM} Z_A \quad (4)$$

Since the three chemical species are assumed to form an ideal solution, each equilibrium mole fraction is equal to the corresponding a_i , and hence equation (4) becomes

$$(1 - a_A - a_B) / a_B = K_{AB} a_A \quad (5)$$

In order to evaluate K_{AM} using equation (5), the observed activities of the components of these binary mixtures were corrected for their dispersion contribution^{7,8}. According to them the corrected activities are

$$a_A = x_A \gamma_A / \gamma_A^* \text{ and } a_B = x_B \gamma_B / \gamma_B^* \quad (6)$$

where γ_A^* and γ_B^* are the activity coefficients of a reference mixture. A mixture of DBE (A) and cyclohexane (B) was chosen as the reference system since the cyclohexane is inert and has nearly the

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same molar volume as the aromatic hydrocarbons. The values of $(1-a_A-a_B)/a_B$ for all these systems were computed and plotted against a_A and the plots were found to be reasonably good straight lines (Fig. 3) passing through the origins except for very high values of a_A . The value of K_{AM} were calculated from the slopes of these graphs and are found to be 1.129, 1.506, 2.974 and 3.000 for DBE+benzene, +toluene, +*o*-xylene and +*m*-xylene mixtures respectively.

Fig. 3. Plots between $(1-a_A-a_B)/a_B$ and a_A for : (O) DBE + benzene, (●) DBE + toluene, (□) DBE + *o*-xylene and (▲) DBE + *m*-xylene.

The unit of concentration was mole fraction in the equilibrium constant obtained from ideal associated model. These were converted into moles/litre and the values are reported in Table 2. Using these values of K , electronic polarisabilities (α_{AB}^e) and dipole moments μ_{AB} for various systems were calculated^{8,9} and are reported in Table 2. The order of variation of α_{AB}^e is DBE+benzene < DBE+toluene < DBE+*o*-xylene < DBE+*m*-xylene, and μ_{AB} varies as DBE+benzene < DBE+toluene < DBE+*m*-xylene < DBE+*o*-xylene. The magnitude of K is a measure of

tendency to form AB type complex in various mixtures. The order of variation of K is DBE+benzene < DBE + toluene < DBE + *o*-xylene \approx DBE + *m*-xylene. The electron donating power of benzene is less than that of toluene and which in turn is less than that of xylenes. The order of variation of K substantiates this conjecture. This is also supported by the order of variation of the electronic polarisabilities of these binary mixtures. The magnitudes of μ_{AB} for these systems indicate that Br-atoms of the DBE molecule point towards the aromatic ring. It appears that some charge from the π -electron cloud of the aromatic ring has been transferred to Br-atoms of DBE.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF PARAMETERS CALCULATED FROM BUEP-BARON MODEL OF COMPLEX FORMATION*

System	K $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	α_{AB}^e NAV ml	μ_{AB} Debye
DBE (A)+ Benzene (B)	0.100 4	53.24	1.12
DBE (A)+Toluene (B)	0.145 4	58.14	1.18
DBE (A)+ <i>o</i> -Xylene (B)	0.303 4	62.93	1.28
DBE (A)+ <i>m</i> -Xylene (B)	0.308 5	63.12	1.18

*The maximum deviation in the calculated values of α_{AB}^e was less than 0.02% and μ_{AB} less than 1%.

Experimental

1,2-Dibromoethane (DBE), benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene and *m*-xylene (all AnalaR) were purified by standard procedures¹⁰. The purities of final samples were checked by density determination (dilatometrically) which agreed to within $\pm 5 \times 10^{-5}$ g cm⁻³ with the corresponding literatures values^{5,11}. Dielectric constant (± 0.0001) was determined from capacity measurement using a dipole meter. The samples were placed in a cell consisting of two coaxial brass cylinders. The cell was immersed in a water at 308.15 K (± 0.01 K) and was calibrated with several liquids of known dielectric constants. The refractive index (± 0.0001) was measured with the help of an Abbe's refractometer at the required temperature (308.15 K). The experimentally obtained dielectric constants and refractive indices for the pure components alongwith their literature values^{12,13} are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3—DENSITY (ρ), DIPOLE MOMENT (μ), ELECTRONIC POLARISABILITIES (α^e), PERMITTIVITY (ϵ) AND REFRACTIVE INDEX OF PURE LIQUIDS AT 308.15 K

Compd.	ρ g cm ⁻³	μ Debye	α^e NAV ml	ϵ		n_D	
				Exptl.	Lit. ^e	Exptl.	Lit. ^f
1,2-Dibromoethane	2.149 50 ^a	1.12 ^c	27.039	4.690 3	NA	1.530 4	1.530 52
Benzene	0.863 30 ^b	0.00 ^c	26.197	2.255 2	2.255 4	1.491 5	1.491 65
Toluene	0.853 10 ^b	0.36 ^d	31.111	2.355 8	2.355 9	1.488 7	1.488 75
<i>o</i> -Xylene	0.857 28 ^a	0.62 ^c	35.888	2.550 4	2.550 5	1.497 8	1.437 92
<i>m</i> -Xylene	0.851 02 ^a	0.37 ^c	36.077	2.370 3	2.370 5	1.489 9	1.489 97

^aRef. 11. ^bRef. 5. ^cRef. 9. ^dRef. 14. ^eRef. 12. ^fRef. 13. NA \equiv literature value at 308.15 K for comparison is not available.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (D.C.S.) thanks C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for awarding a Research Associateship.

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